

Bristol Composites Institute

Fibre length distribution measurement of reclaimed carbon fibres to assess chopping procedures

Patrick Sullivan, Prof. Steve Eichhorn, Prof. Ian Hamerton, Dr Vicky Summers

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How can we enable a supply chain to recycle end-of-life composite components?

How do we encourage industry to use recycled composite materials?

What does composite recycling look like?

Context

Extracted $\approx 50\%$ weight of two A320 VTPs as CFRP panels

Context

Panels shredded and fibres reclaimed using pyrolysis

Produced new discontinuous fibre format materials

Bulk moulding compound (BMC)

- 20% fibre content
- Fibre length 12 mm
- Randomly aligned

Non-woven fabric

- Up to 30% fibre volume fraction
- Fibre length 80 mm
- Some alignment

HiPerDiF highly aligned tape

- Up to 50% fibre volume fraction
- Fibre length 3 - 12 mm
- High alignment

Context

Manufactured a second life component using rCF materials

Wheelchair ramp manufactured by vacuum infusion of carded nonwoven rCF fabric with Arkema Elium, FVF = 13%

Why is fibre length control an issue?

Methodology

	Sample	Original Fibre Length	Chopping Technique	Target Length
Run 1: Short rCF + manual cut	rCF(p)	$l_0 = 80\text{mm}$	Rotary	4mm
Run 2: Short rCF + semi-automatic cut	rCF(p)	$l_0 = 80\text{mm}$	Depositor	4.5mm
Run 3: Long rCF + semi-automatic cut	rCF(s)	$l_0 = 950\text{mm}$	Depositor	4.5mm
Run 4: Long vCF + semi-automatic cut	vCF	$l_0 = 950\text{mm}$	Depositor	4.5mm

80 mm long pyrolyzed fibres, rCF(p)

950 mm long steam-pyrolyzed fibres, rCF(s)

Depositor chopping method

- Model GRC6000rpm pneumatic motor-powered glass fibre depositor
- Cutting cylinder with 24 slots for steel blades at an angular resolution of 15°
- Output lengths limited to multiples of 4.5 mm
- Semi-automatic process due to manual feeding

Methodology

Fibre length distribution measurement method

- FASEP 3E Eco partially automated system used previously for glass fibres^{[1][2]} and natural fibres
- Fibre samples dispersed in water and diluted to a concentration level of 20 to 40 mg per litre
- 4800dpi resolution scan taken of fibre sample before image analysis method used to determine fibre length distribution
- Objects in the image categorised and excluded based on a minimum width criteria
- Clusters interpreted using Hough transform

Defining objects in the scan

Defining the area for analysis

Results

*Hand chopping
L = 80 mm
Pyrolysed fibre*

Results

*Semi-automatic
L = 80 mm
Pyrolysed fibre*

Results

*Semi-automatic
L = 950 mm
Steam-pyrolysed fibre*

Results

*Semi-automatic
L = 950 mm
Virgin fibre*

Results

	Target Length (mm)	Median fibre length (mm)	Target length $\pm 25\%$	Mode $\sim 4\text{mm}$ (mm)	$\pm 0.5\text{ mm}$ of mode $\sim 4\text{mm}$
Run 1: Short rCF + manual cut	4.0	1.74	27%	4.20	18%
Run 2: Short rCF + semi-automatic cut	4.5	3.19	42%	4.80	20%
Run 3: Long rCF + semi-automatic cut	4.5	3.00	42%	4.81	31%
Run 4: Long vCF + semi-automatic cut	4.5	3.31	73%	4.73	58%

- Significantly higher frequency of shorter fibres in the reclaimed samples for all chopping methods
- Longer original fibre length improves precision when using the depositor
- Chopping virgin fibre using the depositor is more precise and accurate than reclaimed fibre

Hand chopping, rCF, $L_0 = 80\text{mm}$

Depositor, rCF, $L_0 = 80\text{mm}$

Depositor, rCF, $L_0 = 950\text{mm}$

Depositor, vCF, $L_0 = 950\text{mm}$

Impact

- The chopping of reclaimed fibre is unlikely to produce a single value result.
- By having a robust method for measuring fibre length distribution, discontinuous reclaimed carbon fibre materials can be characterised including fibre length variability.
- Recycled carbon fibre components can be designed with more confidence and predictive models can be applied.

Fibre length distribution
measurement

Representative
mathematical model

Predictive model for stiffness
and strength

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Any questions?

patrick.sullivan@bristol.ac.uk

patrick.sullivan@nccuk.com

bristol.ac.uk/composites